

Development of material verification test procedure for edge glow protection performance

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1. ABSTRACT

When a high current density flows in a Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) part, the resulting voltage drops within the material associated with the strong electrical anisotropy of the laminate can lead to electrical breakdowns or hotspots at the cut edges of the material or on the inner surface of the panel. The phenomenon occurring at the edge is called “Edge Glow” which can be considered as an ignition hazard.

In order to limit its intensity or even better, to avoid the phenomenon to occur, much work has been performed in order to improve the equipotentiality of the carbon layers in the bulk of the laminate by increasing the transverse conductivity (i.e. Z-conductivity) through the introduction of electrical contacts between plies.

In order to validate a new CFRP material, the performance assessment was based on a lightning test performed on several T-joints which were very expensive and time consuming to manufacture, making the overall development process slow and not compatible with the program objectives and constraints.

In order to support the development of new carbon material in a more efficient way, a simplified assessment test is presented in this paper that focuses only on the performance against edge glow independently from the final assembly solution. In that respect, the Edge Glow protection performance becomes inherent to the material properties and does not depend any more on the detailed design of the part, which is exactly the target set for future composite tank developments.

With this new method, the sample is made of one small coupon of CFRP with 2 fasteners installed in interference fit and misaligned to enhance voltage drop apparition under direct current injection. Although it was not possible to link directly macroscopic parameters such as the voltage drop and current with the microscopic phenomenon associated with the apparition of light at cut edges, this method, based on camera measurements, enabled a quick and economical assessment of the performance for a new material against edge glow.

2. INTRODUCTION

The use of composite material for aircraft wing structures has led to major issues regarding the protection of fuel tanks against lightning direct effects. Several sources of ignition can be created in the composite assembly due to the lightning current flow. There are sparks at the fastener level due to voltage spark between the nut and the internal structure or due to the escape of confined sparks between the fastener itself and the composite structure, called outgassing. An additional

electrical hazard appeared with the introduction of mechanically improved carbon composite materials, commonly called edge glow. This phenomenon occurs at the edge of composite assemblies, in the vicinity of a fastener struck by lightning.

Fig. 1. Lightning ignition source inside composite fuel tank

Edge glow is mainly related to the laminate structure of composite with the separation of conductive layers made of carbon fibres by non-conductive layers made of resin. There are 2 regimes. The first one is linked to the anisotropy of structure which leads to high voltage drop in the material which results in electrical breakdown at the edge of the panel between two carbon plies, not necessarily adjacent in the layup. It occurs at the early stage of the lightning strike, where the voltage drop is the highest. The second one is due to the power deposited into existing contacts at the edge which leads to overheating and therefore hot spots. This type of edge glow has a slower chronology and can be sometimes hidden by the voltage edge glow. The analysis of these phenomena was presented in [1] and [2].

During the previous aircraft program, the development of the lightning strike protections against edge glow and its demonstration was made on complex samples, called T-joint, based on knowledge of the design assembly (external and internal structures, surface protection, fasteners...).

Fig. 2. T-joint sample configuration

Such a sample is very expensive, with a long lead time for manufacturing (few months) and requires a complex lab test set up for current injection/extraction and measurements. Such methodology can only be implemented late in the program development when the design is almost frozen, making the orientation and the validation of solutions for lightning protection difficult.

As mentioned above, the composite material is a key driver in the protection performance in regards to edge glow risk. There is therefore a strong interest to build a simplified approach focused on the material itself for the lightning protection assessment that can be deployed at the earliest stages of material development. Such new methodology, which will be presented in the paper, is an enabler to develop out of cycle material solutions and prepare the development of future aircraft designs.

3. EXISTING AND FUTURE AIRCRAFT DEVELOPMENT

3.1 Certification approach & industrial impact

The certification compliance demonstration for A350 was framed by the regulation evolution of FAR 25.981(a)(3) requiring double fault tolerant design for the protection against ignition source in the fuel tank due to lightning strike. Due to its impracticability, FAA defined special conditions [3] accepting two independent layers of protection against each ignition source as a mean of compliance. In this context, Airbus has chosen to apply these protection features on the complete fuel tank, independently of the lightning zoning [4].

In regards to edge glow, the following layers of protection were applied:

1. Fastener contact with the surface lightning strike protection: ECF (Expanded Copper Foil) in order to divert the current from the internal part and limit the voltage drop or the power deposited below the edge glow threshold
2. Edge oversealant capable of containing any edge glow condition resulting from potential failure of the first layer

Fig. 3. Edge glow layers of protection

The efficiency of the first layer of protection is highly dependent on the proximity of the fastener head with the ECF in order to decrease the voltage drop in the laminate [2]. This requires a thick ECF but also tight tolerances for fastener installation to prevent deep countersink and negative contact height.

Fig. 4. Contact height between fastener and ECF

The efficiency of the second layer of protection relies on a larger application of oversealant than the nominal edge seal required for fuel tightness.

Fig. 5. Fillet sealing vs oversealant

These protection features represent weight and recurring cost penalty but also manufacturing constraints with additional inspection to ensure their reliability.

In the context of future aircraft development, high production rates are targeted. Therefore, there is a strong interest in removing these layers of protection to alleviate constraints on production and suppress risk of quality escape.

3.2 Edge glow free target principle

Lightning threat that was originally in FAR 25.981 is now addressed by CS/FAR 25.954. The compliance shall demonstrate the prevention of catastrophic fuel vapour ignition. A design based on fault tolerant approach with 2 layers of protection as developed for A350 could be implemented again for a future aircraft but a design demonstrated as being intrinsically safe is also an acceptable approach. As defined in AC25.954 [5], an intrinsically safe lightning protection is due to a reliable design or to a very low lightning threat which cannot create an ignition source. In the case of edge glow protection, this can be achieved by the development of new composite materials enabling the distribution of the current through the laminate thickness, while limiting the voltage drop between plies and energy deposition at the edge of the panel. This is what we will call an “edge glow free” material.

Such material development is a long process in order to fulfil all the requirements regarding lightning performance, but also mechanical and manufacturing performances. Indeed, this is not compatible with the planning of an aircraft development and this cannot be done in parallel without entering into the critical path. As a consequence, it is essential to develop out-of-cycle solutions in order to be prepared prior to the start of a new program. To support such an approach, it is necessary to define an evaluation method focused on the material and independently from the detailed assembly design.

4. MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT: FROM T-JOINT TO SMALL COUPON

A T-joint sample as presented in Fig. 2. is a large scale sample to represent a wing structural assembly made of an external skin and an internal part such as a spar. The large sample size and the boundary conditions for current return is chosen to ensure a representative current distribution into the assembly. Still, the generation of edge glow is related to the voltage rise of the injection bolt that is partly transferred to the surrounding edges through carbon fibers in contact with the bolt.

To understand the phenomenon, it has been first considered that a test sample can be limited to a 2 bolts assembly [2].

Fig. 6. Reduced sample assembly

This is a conservative approach to keep only one bolt in addition to the one used for the injection (second fastener on the next figure) since the suppressed row of bolts contributes to the limitation of the voltage drop between plies. The current is injected into one fastener with the ground on two of the four edges of the sample. In addition, the bolts are misaligned in order to suppress any direct conductive path with the fibres in the 0° direction. In this configuration, the voltage drop between plies is enhanced. In addition, the size of the sample is adapted to obtain the shortest distance acceptable per design between the bolts and from the edge.

Such a sample provides the advantage to simulate the distribution of the current between the surface lightning strike protection, the composite skin and the internal part with injection of the complete lightning threat. But the amount of current that will flow into the spar, where the edge glow occurs, is highly dependent on the current diverted by the surface lightning strike protection thanks to the contact with the bolt. As a consequence, there is a variability in the results related to the installation of the bolt and its countersink depth that partly screens the intrinsic spar material performance with regards to edge glow

Thus, for the material evaluation purpose, it is essential to define a repeatable and stable test method. Since the edge glow occurs on the internal part cut edges, the sample can be further simplified with the removal of the external skin in the assembly. In that case, the current injected into the sample is a fraction of the complete threat according to the distribution of current between the top skin and the spar that can be obtained from numerical simulations.

Fig. 7. Edge glow sample simplification

Previous works have demonstrated that the observed phenomena at the edge is directly related to the voltage drop between bolts and power deposition into the spar, that are both related to the level of current injected. As a consequence, it is here needed to demonstrate that the same level of stress in the spar is developed (and therefore same edge glow phenomena) for this second (sample reduction whatever the sample type (reduced assembly or spar sample) provided that the current injected into the spar is the same.

The variability related to current injection with an arc on the head of the fastener can be removed for the spar sample thanks to a conducted current injection into a protruding head with a metallic bracket. Then, to ensure a good contact between the bolts and the composite plies, an installation in interference is needed. The bolt head and the nut are insulated from the laminate by the use of non-conductive washers. Finally, oversealant is applied on bolt heads and nuts to contain any unwanted outgassing that would pollute the test analysis for edge glow.

Fig. 8. Spar sample detailed configuration

The current amplitude flowing through the spar depends on several parameters such as the top surface protection density (ECF), the skin thickness and electrical conductivity, the electrical continuity between the impacted bolt and the ECF and the bolts misalignment. It depends also on spar properties such as the thickness, the layup and electrical conductivities along the fibers (σ_x), perpendicular to fibers within a ply (σ_y) and across the thickness, also called in-depth conductivity (σ_z). Thanks to a 3D model of a complete assembly based on a wire approach [6], we have assessed the level of current flowing through the spar and its dependence with material properties, spar layup and number of plies.

Fig. 9. Reduced sample assembly 3D model

Note that every spar ply is represented in the model but the distance between plies is 10 times the real one to ease exploitation of results. As the evaluation has been performed with a Boundary Element Method at very low frequency and using lumped properties, the non-realistic distance has no impact on the results. Results presented on the next graph have been obtained by considering a reference triplet of conductivities of about 40000, 40 and 5S/m (for σ_x , σ_y and σ_z respectively), then varying each conductivity while keeping the other constant.

Fig. 10. Spar current sensitivity to electrical properties (skin properties were kept constant)

Considering a variation of the spar electrical properties only, the in-depth conductivity (σ_z) is the main driver in the current diversion into the spar since this is the conductivity which can be the most improved in the laminate. This strong impact is however related to the hypotheses done. First, only the spar material properties have been varied, the skin properties being kept constant. Secondly, the model used was based on the required condition of a deep countersink corresponding to an absence of contact between the bolt and the ECF layer. This condition was required to demonstrate the inherent performance of the protection with the deactivation of the electrical contact. Consequently, it corresponds to an extreme situation where spar properties have the highest impact as ECF is weakly solicited for the current flow. Indeed, from T-joint experiments with similar skin/spar configuration than that modelled and where the arc root can partly attach to the ECF rim close to the bolt head, no more than 10kA was measured into the spar. Such level is therefore considered as the scaled waveform D [7] for small coupon assessment. This is a first point of reference based on previous design solutions.

Finally, since the objective of the experimental method is to support material development, the final laminate design (layout and number of plies) is supposedly unknown. Using the

numerical model, we assessed the voltage drop between plies, considering this has a direct relation with the edge glow risk. On the next graph, it is presented the maximum voltage drop between two adjacent plies versus the number of plies of the spar.

Fig. 11. Voltage drop between plies versus number of plies

The max voltage drop obviously decreases when the number of plies increases. Indeed, beyond the number of plies, as the voltage drop is the highest across the $-45^\circ/45^\circ$ plies interface (due to the staggered installation of the bolts), the max voltage drop decrease is directly sensitive to the number of $-45^\circ/45^\circ$ couples. Then, the influence of the stacking sequence, defining the layout of the laminate with the different ply orientation (0° , 90° , 45° , -45°), for a given number of $-45^\circ/45^\circ$ couples, is more limited.

Therefore, in order to ensure the worst case condition, the minimum expected number of plies shall be chosen. When studying different material grades which will modify the ply thickness, it is necessary to target the same total laminate thickness and adapt the number of plies accordingly as it will be the case for a structural assembly to comply with the mechanical constraints.

5. EVALUATION METHOD AND CRITERIA

The objective of this evaluation method is to support the development of new composite materials for fuel tank structure managing the risk of edge glow. This can be used for the change of material for an existing aircraft or for a complete new application for a future aircraft. In the first case, the performance of the material can be targeted to be equivalent to the baseline where edge glow protection is based on 2 protection layers. The material would be called here “edge glow compliant”. For the second case, the performance target should be more ambitious and remove completely the edge glow risk. The material is then “edge glow free”.

The method is built to assess and classify the performance of new materials in order to orientate material suppliers in the most optimised solution. Therefore, we need to define conditions where edge glows are deliberately created to increase their intensity and enable a comparison between different material solutions. Since this is not a simple pass/fail criteria as made for certification where a spark visible by the camera is a fail, it is necessary to propose a different approach.

SAE AE-2 ARP5416 working group and EUROCAE working group 31 developed a new photographic method in order to

assess the ignition risk [8]. The camera is set up and verified by the laboratory with a spark gap to enable the detection of 200µJ sparks. With this method, the camera settings are identified and fixed for the tests. A quantitative threshold, called ignition threshold pixel value, is defined to determine the ignition risk related to the energy of the spark based on the maximum pixel value (from 0 to 255), equivalent to the brightness of the spark. This is an interesting technique to support the quantification of the edge glow intensity and therefore the comparison between materials.

5.1 Lightning tests

With a test at 10kA as defined above, a material having not shown a source of ignition can be considered as a very good candidate for being edge glow free. Its max pixel value shall be below the ignition threshold pixel value or even in the noise level (i.e. no edge glow) to demonstrate its performance. For an edge glow compliant material, this will depend on the targeted application where oversealant is capable of confining the produced edge glow on the aircraft assembly. Here below is an example of an edge glow compliant material result. In order to locate the edge glow, the reference picture was superimposed with the lightning test picture.

Fig. 12. Edge glow compliant low level test result (10kA)

Since it will be difficult to discriminate the performance of different materials with edge glow of very low energy, it is necessary to consider tests with very high levels of current in order to expand the scale of performance assessment. For this purpose, tests with injected currents of 30kA were added to the test procedure. At such a level, more powerful edge glows are expected as materials are overstressed and therefore the criteria cannot rely on the maximum pixel value. The ignition surface is now computed and used as the classification criteria. This surface corresponds to the surface in mm² occupied by the edge glow pixels with a value above the ignition threshold pixel value defined by the camera verification. Those pixels will be called “ignition pixels”. In the next picture, it is presented a comparison between an edge glow free material with an ignition surface of about 5mm² and an edge glow compliant material with about 6000mm² of ignition surface.

Fig. 13. Edge glow free (top) vs compliant (bottom) high level test results (30kA)

With this level, it is possible to clearly discriminate against both material behaviour. It shall be noted that the objective is not to reproduce edge glow expected on an aircraft assembly as the powerful edge glow produced during high level tests is obtained with injected currents far above the real current levels flowing through the spar. On edge glow compliant materials like those on A350, limited edge glows were observed when both protection features were disabled. The results is presented in the figure below:

Fig. 14. Edge glow with protections features disabled

With the combination of both test results, it is possible to assess the material in different stress regimes and highlight any unusual behaviour.

Moreover, the performance of a material in regards to edge glow is linked to its ability to transfer the current in the laminate with a limited stress in the material, which directly depends on its transverse electrical conductivity. The stability of this property shall be ensured throughout the laminate. The manufacturing parameters controlling the performance of the material must be identified and their respective significance understood. From there, the manufacturing process must integrate the necessary controls to ensure that the expected performance is inherently reproduced on all material batches. For example, an uneven impregnation of the carbon laminate could lead to a different contact distribution that would be detrimental for the transverse conductivity. Therefore, a minimum of 3 samples per test level is required. The next graph presents the max pixel value results for different materials, M1 to M11 and identified by a different colour.

Fig. 15. Examples of max pixel value results obtained with 11 different materials using the low level test procedure (10kA)

Based on such results, a decision can be made to move for the next step in the material selection or to launch additional investigations. Among those examples, M1 and M2 tend to demonstrate edge glow free behaviour since no edge glow was detected at all. It has to be noticed that a black picture presents a noise floor in the pixel value (~50). This performance needs to be confirmed with high level tests (30kA). On the other hand, M3 can be discarded since it produces an already powerful edge glow even at low level. From material M4 to M7, especially for M7, an investigation is required to identify the key features which provide the performance and understand the root cause of the variability observed.

5.2 Conductivity test

As mentioned earlier, the improvement of the transverse conductivity (σ_z) is a way to mitigate edge glow risk. Therefore, it is part of the evaluation method to easily assess the possible performance of a material prior to any lightning test. This conductivity test is made on square samples extracted from the same laminate panel built for the lightning test samples. The resistance of the sample is measured between the top and the bottom surface and the transverse conductivity is extracted from the resistance measurement, supposing a homogeneous material along the thickness [6].

For a usual thermoset laminate structure, a conductivity of more than 20 S/m will ensure a very good performance of the material to mitigate edge glow phenomenon. On the other hand, a conductivity lower than 1S/m presents a high risk of edge glow apparition and could require a modification of the material before making the decision to use the material on a new program. Now, the conductivity is a macroscopic parameter and does not give any information on how the conductivity is ensured between plies and how much it is homogenous at microscopic level, stable, controlled and reliable under high current stress. Thus, this cannot be the only criteria to predict the performance of a material and for this reason, lightning tests on small coupons are still necessary. Looking at the ignition surface results during high current level tests on different materials, the improvement of the conductivity tends to decrease the edge glow risk. But different types of material or architecture would change the scale of conductivity required. For example, infusion materials with fabric plies represent a completely different structure compared to thermoset laminate. Therefore, the different mechanisms creating, at the microscale level, the electrical contacts ensuring the lightning current flow will lead to a different conductivity value at the macroscale level. Good edge glow performance could be achieved with lower conductivity than unidirectional material with clear interply separation. The figure below illustrates the different families

of materials with different ranges of edge glow risk evolution with the conductivity. For the materials with no ignition surface, the value was arbitrarily set to 10-8mm² to be visible on the log scale.

Fig. 16. Ignition surface evolution with conductivity

5.3 Investigations and next steps

This screening procedure has been used for around a hundred different materials. Such an approach would never have been possible with the previous test procedure based on T-joint. Based on these 3 simple tests (10kA lightning test, 30kA lightning test and conductivity test), it is possible to assess the performance of a material and to rank it for a given target. This is a key enabler to work in a close collaboration with the suppliers and converge on an acceptable solution for a moderate cost. But this is the first step towards certification. Since edge glow risk is dependent on the material architecture, it is necessary to understand the key features which will influence the material performance and how it can be modified by the material production and component manufacturing. This could require complementary tests to assess the sensitivity of edge glow prevention with the manufacturing tolerances. At the final stage of this pyramidal qualification, T-joint tests with conditions introducing multiple degradation to verify the inherent nature of the anti-edge glow performance are required in the context of the targeted fuel tank design principles. The lightning threat in the spar will then be representative of the one seen by a real aircraft assembly.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a disruptive method to assess the edge glow risk related to a CFRP structure. Based on the understanding of the main drivers at the origin of this phenomena, it was possible to simplify the lightning tests performed on a massive sample (T-joint) to an elementary coupon with only 2 bolts. It represents a good advantage since it allows the development of new material without knowing the detailed design assembly. Since the development of material can take years to be finalised, this is an important step to enable out-of-cycle solutions ready for the next program. Due to the burden of implementing protection features against edge glow, the target for a future aircraft is an intrinsically safe material, i.e. an edge glow free material.

This principle of the method proposed is to support new materials screening and scale their performances. For this purpose, the test sample is designed (ply number, stacking sequence and bolts arrangement) to produce an envelope regarding the lightning stress leading to edge glow. The intensity of the edge glow is then assessed at 2 different levels of electrical stress (10kA and 30kA). A third test to measure

the transverse conductivity is added to complement the evidence linked to the ability of the material to transfer the current with a limited stress. The conductivity value must be interpreted with the knowledge of the material architecture.

This evaluation method is the first step to identify the good material solution. The next steps will be to identify the material features providing its performance and to ensure their stability throughout the industrialisation process. Finally, the compliance demonstration will be based on a final T-joint test with the complete representative design assembly.

7. REFERENCES

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